

ASSESSMENT OF SAFETY MANAGEMENT SYSTEM IN BRICK/BLOCK LAYING AND CONCRETING WORKSHOPS IN TECHNICAL COLLEGES OF KADUNA STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract

The study assessed Safety Management System in Brick/Block Laying and Concreting Workshops in Technical Colleges of Kaduna State, Nigeria. The study had five objectives. In line with the objectives, five research questions and five hypotheses were raised. Descriptive survey research design was used for the study. The population of the study was 153 brick/block laying and concreting workshops teachers, workshop assistants and NTC in technical colleges in 2021/2020 academic session. 18 teachers, 11 workshop assistants, 128 NTC 1 were randomly sampled and used for the study. The instrument for data collection was a 4-point rating scale structured questionnaire. The instrument was validated by four experts. Cronbach Alpha was used to test the reliability and reliability coefficient of ≥ 0.70 was obtained. The data were collected by the researcher assisted by two research assistants using direct contact. The exercise lasted for three weeks. Description Statistics of (mean) was used to answer the research questions. The result revealed, among others, that safety policy, promotion, risk management, assurance and litigation in brick/block laying and concreting workshop were adhered and followed by the teachers and workshop assistants, and there was significant difference between the responses of the teachers and workshop assistants, while safety litigation shows that, there was no significance differences between the responses of teachers and workshop assistants in technical colleges of Kaduna State. It was concluded to improve the brick/block laying and concreting workshops safety management system, there is need to build the capacity of lecturers and workshop assistance in Safety policy, promotion, risk management, assurance and litigation in Brick/Block Laying and Concreting Workshop at Technical Colleges were followed based on the findings of the study. It was recommended, among others, that safety policy, safety promotion, safety risk management, safety assurance and safety litigation in brick/block laying and concreting workshop teachers and workshop assistants should be retrained for improving students' performance in Concreting Workshop at Technical Colleges in Kaduna state, Nigeria.

Keywords: Safety Management System, Brick/Block Laying and Concreting, Technical Colleges

Introduction

Occupational safety is of paramount concern to both workers and students. Students and even parents are much more interested in the level of safety provided in a particular occupation. Graduates who possess required safety skills would always fair better in an occupation, especially technical occupations. The knowledge of safety practice skills by building construction students in technical colleges is an essential prerequisite for effective use of tools and machines in the workshops. Skilled electrical worker is not just

someone who can perform any electrical job correctly but a worker who can complete every job safely (Oranu, Nwoke and Ogwo, 2012). Safety has become a major determinant for effective and successful performance in a job.

Accidents in the brick/block laying and concreting school work-shops remain an ongoing concern in the developing countries, despite the level of awareness in promoting safety management system over the decades. Safety management system in the brick/block laying and concreting workshop is anchored on students' behaviour regarding safety provisions, conducts that guides students' attitude in carrying out their tasks in the workshop in order to reduce or even eliminate accidental losses and injuries (Umoh, 2013). Perceived increment in number of casualties and illnesses reported in brick/block laying and concreting workshops in Kaduna State Technical Colleges are unacceptably high considering the numerous regulatory standards and control systems for construction projects, thereby creating serious menace to brick/block layers and concreter health at work. Thus, proactive step must be taken to identify these factors and be averted accordingly. It is against this backdrop that the researcher intends to carry out research on the assessment of Safety Management system in brick/block laying and concreting Workshops at Technical Colleges in Kaduna State.

Research Questions

The study answered the following research questions:

1. What are the safety policy in Block/Brick-laying and concreting workshops at Technical Colleges in Kaduna State?
2. What are the safety promotion in Block/Brick-laying and concreting workshops at Technical Colleges in Kaduna State?
3. What are the safety risk management in Block/Brick-laying and concreting workshops at Technical Colleges in Kaduna State?
4. What are the safety assurance in Block/Brick-laying and concreting workshops at Technical Colleges in Kaduna State?
5. What are the safety litigation in Block/Brick-laying and concreting workshops at Technical Colleges in Kaduna State?

Methodology

The study used descriptive survey research design. The area of the study was Kaduna State. The study covered all the seven (7) technical colleges in the state. The population for the study was made up of all the 153 brick/block laying and concreting workshops' teachers, workshop assistants and students in technical colleges of Kaduna State. 153 entire population were used for the study because it is of manageable size. The instrument for data collection was structured questionnaire. The questionnaire was developed by the researcher from the available literature on brick/block laying and concreting workshops safety management system. on safety promotion in brick/block laying and concreting workshops. The instruments were administered on the respondents by the researcher through personal contacts with the respondents and with the help of two research assistants. For

analysing the data, mean and standard deviation were used answer the research questions.

Results

Research Question One

What are the Safety Policy in Brick/Block Laying and Concreting Workshop at Technical Colleges in Kaduna State?

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation on the responses of Teachers, Workshop Assistants and Students on Safety policies in brick/block laying and concreting workshop assistants

S/N	Items	Respondents							Remarks
		n _T = 18, n _A = 7, n _S = 128							
		\bar{x}_T	σ_T	\bar{x}_A	σ_A	\bar{x}_S	σ_S	\bar{x}_g	
1.	Never use the workshop alone	3.06	.802	3.29	.756	2.88	.561	2.92	A
2.	DO NOT perform a task you are uncomfortable with	3.61	.778	3.71	.488	3.10	.303	3.19	A
3.	Eye protection is required when construction is taking place in the shop	3.11	.758	4.00	.522	3.10	.303	3.14	A
4.	Work gloves are available	3.00	.907	3.71	.488	3.10	.303	3.12	A
5.	Dust masks are needed	2.72	1.364	3.57	.535	3.29	.455	3.24	A
6.	Earplugs are needed	3.61	.778	3.29	.756	3.51	.676	3.51	SA
7.	No toxic fumes inside the shop	2.29	1.27	3.29	.756	2.20	.404	2.26	DA
8.	Maintain a clean work area	3.22	.943	3.00	.577	3.20	.404	3.19	A
9.	Report injuries to shop supervisor	3.06	.873	2.86	.690	3.20	.404	3.17	A
10.	Do NOT leave projects in workshop unless they are stored in a bin or in a table cubbie	3.83	.383	2.71	1.25	3.34	.477	3.37	A
Cluster Mean		3.21		3.34		3.19		3.19	

Result on Safety Policies in Brick/Block Laying and Concreting is presented in Table 1, the result revealed that mean responses of Technical Colleges Teachers, Workshop Assistants and Students in Technical Colleges of Kaduna State. The table 1 indicated that 9 items ranges from 1-6 and 8-10 had a mean response ranging from 2.90 – 3.51 which shows that the respondents agreed with all the items. However, items 7 of which says that no toxic fumes inside the workshops was disagreed by all the respondents respectively on safety policy.

Research Question Two

What are the Safety Promotion in Brick/Block Laying and Concreting Workshop at Technical Colleges in Kaduna State?

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation on the responses of Teachers, Workshop Assistants and Students on Safety Promotion in brick/block laying and concreting workshop assistants

S/N	Items	Respondents n _T = 18, n _A = 7, n _S = 128							Remarks
		\bar{x}_T	σ_T	\bar{x}_A	σ_A	\bar{x}_S	σ_S	\bar{x}_g	
1.	School has established clear policies	3.83	.383	3.86	.378	3.58	.496	3.62	SA
2.	School reinforces goals to the later	3.44	1.149	3.00	1.00	3.48	.501	3.45	A
3.	School Assess classroom and self	2.61	1.501	3.00	.816	3.48	.501	3.36	A
4.	School is being purposeful about being inclusive	3.39	.979	3.14	.690	3.43	.497	3.41	A
5.	School encourages reporting technical events	3.00	.970	3.43	.535	3.39	.490	3.35	A
6.	School is made more approachable	3.72	.575	3.57	.535	3.41	.727	3.45	A
7.	School Involve parents, family and community members	3.72	.461	3.29	1.11	3.09	.804	3.17	A
8.	School Provide support to targets	3.56	.511	2.86	1.34	3.32	.651	3.33	A
9.	School Teach civics	3.39	.502	3.29	.756	3.28	.451	3.29	A
10.	School Inspire ally behaviour	3.56	.511	2.86	.690	3.15	.576	3.18	A
Cluster Mean		3.42		3.23		3.36		3.36	

Result on Safety Promotion in Brick/Block Laying and Concreting was presented in Table 2. This clearly indicated that all the items 1-10 which had the mean response ranging from 3.17 – 3.62 shows that the respondents agreed with all the items on safety promotion in Brick/Block Laying and Concreting workshop in Kaduna state.

Research Question Three

What are the Safety Risk Management in Brick/Block Laying and Concreting Workshop at Technical Colleges in Kaduna State?

Table 3: Mean and Standard Deviation on the responses of Teachers, Workshop Assistants and Students on Safety Risk Management in brick/block laying and concreting

S/N	Items	Respondents							Remarks
		n _T = 18, n _A = 7, n _S = 128							
		\bar{x}_T	σ_T	\bar{x}_A	σ_A	\bar{x}_S	σ_S	\bar{x}_g	
1.	Access to the workshop machining areas are strictly restricted to authorized personnel only	3.39	.502	3.86	.378	3.33	.653	3.36	A
2.	No one may operate workshop equipment unless they have received sufficient training	3.56	.511	3.57	.535	3.30	.462	3.34	A
3.	Guards on machine are used	3.39	.502	3.71	.488	3.35	.479	3.37	A
4.	All workshop equipment must be regularly maintained and serviced	3.72	.461	3.71	.488	3.38	.664	3.44	SA
5.	Long hair are completely covered	3.83	.383	3.43	.535	3.52	.676	3.55	SA
6.	Suitable eye protection worn	3.78	.548	3.14	.378	3.55	.929	3.56	SA
7.	Electrical equipment is always operated in accordance to manufacturer's instructions	3.67	.594	3.14	.378	3.38	.664	3.40	A
8.	Any defective equipment will be reported to the technician in charge	3.78	.428	3.43	.535	3.17	.870	3.25	A
9.	A risk assessment must be completed for lifting heavy loads	3.78	.647	3.29	.488	3.37	.484	3.41	A
10.	Appropriate PPE for lifting operations must be worn	3.33	.485	3.71	.488	3.18	.873	3.22	A
Cluster Mean		3.62		3.49		3.35		3.39	

Result on Safety Risk Management in Brick/Block Laying and Concreting is presented in Table 3. This clearly indicated that all the items 1-10 which had the mean response ranging from 3.22 to 3.59 shows that the respondents agree with all the items on safety risk management in Brick/Block Laying and Concreting workshop at technical colleges of Kaduna State.

Research Question Four

What are the Safety Assurance in Brick/Block Laying and Concreting Workshop at Technical Colleges in Kaduna State?

Table 4: Mean and Standard Deviation on the responses of Teachers, Workshop Assistants and Students on Safety Assurance in brick/block laying and concreting

S/N	Items	Respondents							Remarks
		n _T = 18, n _A = 7, n _S = 128							
		\bar{x}_T	σ_T	\bar{x}_A	σ_A	\bar{x}_S	σ_S	\bar{x}_g	
1.	The college workshop objectives are clearly defined	3.28	.461	3.86	.378	2.70	.647	2.82	A
2.	The college workshop objectives are clearly understood	3.33	.767	3.57	.535	2.80	.404	2.89	A
3.	The college has a clearly defined approach to risk management	3.50	.985	3.71	.488	2.90	.303	3.01	A
4.	The college’s approach ensures that material impact on the achievement of the college objectives	3.44	.616	3.71	.488	2.94	.585	3.03	A
5.	The college has a clear understanding of risk mitigation including existing controls	3.61	.698	3.43	.535	3.32	.793	3.36	A
6.	The colleges have a clear understanding of risk mitigation including existing planned actions	3.72	.461	3.14	.378	3.08	.694	3.16	A
7.	The college clearly established risk management reporting.	3.83	.383	3.14	.378	3.00	.452	3.10	A
8.	The college has clearly established risk management monitory	3.61	.502	3.43	.535	2.90	.303	3.01	A
9.	The college has established a board assurance policy	3.61	.502	3.29	.488	3.04	.493	3.12	A
10.	There is clearly defined structure within the college that will support the development	3.50	.786	3.71	.488	3.48	.502	3.49	A
Cluster Mean		3.54		3.46		3.02		3.10	

Result on Safety Assurance in Brick/Block Laying and Concreting is presented in Table 4. This also indicated that all the items from 1-10 which had the mean response ranging from 2.82 – 3.49 shows that the respondents agree with all the items in table 4 on safety assurance in Brick Block Laying and Concreting Workshop in Technical Colleges of Kaduna State.

Research Question Five

What are the Safety Litigation in Brick/Block Laying and Concreting Workshop at Technical Colleges in Kaduna State?

Table 5: Mean and Standard Deviation on the responses of Teachers, Workshop Assistants and Students on Safety litigation in brick/block laying and concreting workshop assistants

S/N	Items	Respondents							Remarks
		n _T = 18, n _A = 7, n _S = 128							
		\bar{x}_T	σ_T	\bar{x}_A	σ_A	\bar{x}_S	σ_S	\bar{x}_g	
1.	Enforcing compliance with work health and safety litigation	2.83	.707	3.57	.535	2.57	.535	2.65	A
2.	Monitoring compliance with work health and safety litigation	3.11	.323	3.43	.535	3.43	.535	3.39	A
3.	Providing guidance/advice on work health and safety	3.11	.900	3.29	.488	3.11	.488	2.75	A
4.	Providing information on work health safety	3.58	.623	3.43	.535	2.73	.535	2.86	A
5.	Fostering a co-operative relationship between duties	3.80	.404	3.57	.787	3.57	.787	3.60	SA
6.	Person to whom owe those duties and their representatives	3.86	.349	3.00	.577	3.01	.577	3.05	A
7.	Collecting other information relating to work health	3.33	.471	3.00	.000	3.00	.000	3.04	A
8.	Publishing statistics and other information relating to work health and safety	3.05	.383	3.00	1.00	3.00	1.00	3.01	A
Cluster Mean		2.67		2.62		2.54		2.56	

Result on Safety Litigation in Brick/Block Laying and Concreting is presented in Table 5. This clearly indicated that all the items from 1-8 which had the mean response ranging from 2.65 to 3.60 shows that the respondents agreed with all the items in table 6 on safety litigation in Brick Block Laying and Concreting Workshop in Kaduna State.

Findings of the study

The following were the findings of the study:

1. It was found out that all the respondents agreed that all the items on safety policy in Brick/Block Laying and Concreting Workshop in Technical Colleges of Kaduna state.
2. It was found out that all the respondents agreed on the safety promotion in Brick/Block Laying and Concreting Workshop in Technical Colleges of Kaduna State.
3. It was found out that all the respondents agreed on the safety risk management in Brick/Block Laying and Concreting Workshop in Technical Colleges of Kaduna State.
4. It was found out that all the respondents agreed on the safety assurance in Brick/Block Laying and Concreting Workshop in Technical Colleges of Kaduna State.
5. It was found out that all the respondents agreed on the safety litigation in Brick/Block Laying and Concreting

Workshop in Technical Colleges of Kaduna State.

Discussion of Findings

The result of research question one revealed that respondents agreed that Safety Policy in Brick/Block Laying and Concreting Workshop at Technical Colleges were adhered. This was also confirmed with the test of hypothesis one which indicated that there was significant difference between the responses of the teachers and workshop assistants in terms of safety policies. This finding is in line with that of Ogundipe, Owolabi, Olanipekun, Olaniran, Akuete, and Fagbenle (2018). Which revealed that the top aspect of safety practices currently explored by the indigenous concreting workshop include: provision of accidents prevention procedure and development and frequently review of Safety Policy for building projects.

The result of research question two shows that respondents agreed the result of research question one shows that respondents agreed that Safety Promotion in Brick/Block Laying and Concreting Workshop at Technical Colleges were followed and there was significant difference between the responses of the teachers and workshop assistants in terms of safety promotion. This finding in accordance with Abdullahi (2018) The results showed that a majority of students have between moderate to high level of awareness of workshop safety precaution except in 3 items where students have between low and zero level awareness. The overall result indicates that students have quite a high level of awareness of workshop safety.

The result of research question three revealed that respondents agreed that Safety Risk Management in Brick/Block Laying and Concreting Workshop at Technical Colleges were observed. This finding is line with that of Vitharana, De Silva, and De Silva (2015) The study revealed that lack of awareness about site safety and dislike to wear Personal Protective Equipment (PPE) were identified as main causes of poor safety practices in construction sites.

The result of research question four revealed that respondents agreed that Safety Assurance in Brick/Block Laying and Concreting Workshop at Technical Colleges were adhered. And there was significant difference between the responses of the teachers and workshop assistants in terms of safety assurance. This finding is in line with that of Laryoh (2014) the findings revealed a low level of awareness of safety assurance tools and techniques. More so, safety assurance practices in the various companies were identified to be low. In summary, respondents are not committed to safety assurance on construction sites.

The result of research question five revealed that respondents agreed that Safety Litigation in Brick/Block Laying and Concreting Workshop at Technical Colleges were followed and there was no significant difference between the responses of the teachers and workshop assistants in terms of safety litigation. This is in line with Omozokpia (1994). In his study revealed that teachers' use of various teaching methods and evaluation for safety education depends on teachers' qualification, teaching and industrial experience. Also, Tanko and Anigbogu (2012) in their study revealed that the vast majority of workers understand the need for PPE and want to be protected against accident, injury and illness. However, there is a need to address the issues of comfort with respect to PPE to ensure it does not interfere with worker's productivity and takes into account specific work environment.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that to improve the brick/block laying and concreting workshops safety management system, there is need to build the capacity of teachers', workshop assistance and students in Safety policy, promotion, risk management, assurance and litigation in Brick/Block Laying and Concreting Workshop at Technical Colleges were followed based on the findings of the study.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made based on findings of the study:

1. Teachers, workshop assistants and students should maintain the habit of maintaining safety policy in Brick/Block laying and concreting workshop in Technical Colleges of Kaduna State.
2. Teachers, workshop assistants and students should maintain the awareness on safety promotion in Brick/Block laying and concreting workshop in technical colleges of Kaduna State.
3. There should be no sensitization amongst teachers, workshop assistant and students on the risk management in Brick/Block laying and concreting workshop in Technical Colleges of Kaduna State.
4. There should be more sensitization amongst teachers, workshop assistance and students on safety assurance in Brick/Block laying and concreting workshop in Technical Colleges of Kaduna State.
5. There should be awareness on safety litigation in Brick/Block laying and concreting workshop in Technical Colleges of Kaduna State.

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